

FEATURES IN THE TRANSLATION OF MEDICAL TERMS

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Introduction. The expansion of our country's foreign relations in the field of medicine, the intensive development of professional communication of medical workers in English, German, as well as an increase in the number of specialists involved in international communication, entail an increased interest in the study of medical terminology and the problem of its translation. In the process of perception, understanding, interpretation and translation of medical texts, the main task is to convey to the recipient the deep cognitive content of terminological units in the most clear, clear, concise, familiar form for representatives of the receiving linguistic culture [3, p. 181]. Translation of medical discourse texts requires translators to have a fairly deep theoretical knowledge of this subject area of science, to have some preparation in the practice of written translation, functional stylistics, text linguistics, and also terminology [5, p.

ABSTRACT

The article presents analysis results of translation of medication package inserts from English and German to Russian and Uzbek languages. Data about the frequency of use of the translation techniques that correspond to lexical and grammatical transformations in translated units of any text genre is given. The most frequently used translation techniques are identified: selection of equivalent lexical forms, combination of different techniques, calque translation, and explicatory translation.

576]. The translation process when working with texts of medical discourse is characterized by certain specifics and regularities, which comes to light when studying translation decisions related, inter alia, to medical terminology. In light of the foregoing, the purpose of this article is to analyze the methods for translating medical terms in the texts of instructions for the use of medicines, different in terms of their structure, origin and content.

Key concepts. Medical terms - a set of special items that are understood as standard units of a special item serving the scientific or professional sphere of modern official medicine [1, p. 31-32]. This study considers the term from a linguistic perspective, where the term is a functional lexical unit that takes on the features of the term [6, p. 86]. The term has three groups of requirements: content requirements, form and pragmatic properties. It should be noted that the requirements, in this

case, are a set of characteristics that the term should possess. The first group (requirements for content) includes the following aspects: semantics consistency (correspondence of the meaning of the term as a lexical unit and its meaning in this terminology), unambiguity (the desire for unambiguity within the framework of one terminology), completeness (the minimum number should be reflected in the meaning of the term signs sufficient to identify the concept designated by him) and the absence of synonyms [6, p. 90].

The second group (form requirements) includes: brevity (elimination of meaningless elements), derivational term ability (ability to form new words), compliance with language standards (elimination of deviations from grammatical and phonetic norms, summing up language standards, elimination of professional jargon), the requirement of invariance (invariance of the form of terms) and semantic transparency (display in the structure of a given term of the relationship with this concept, which he calls, etc. ugin concepts) [6, p. 90]. The requirements of the third group (pragmatic) include: modernity (supplanting outdated terms), internationality (matching the form and content of the term in at least three national languages), implantation (adoption of the term by specialists), harmony and esotericism (striving for different formulations for isolating professional communication) [6, p. 90].

Two types of translation operations can be used to convey terms. First, the use of cross-language correspondences (equivalents). Secondly, in the absence of an equivalent, the translator can take the path of creating a new term using

translation techniques such as transliteration or transcription; descriptive translation; the use of tracing is not excluded. Terms that do not have correspondences in the translating language can be attributed to the so-called equivalent vocabulary, and the transfer of the meanings of equivalent terms is subject to the same rules by which nonequivalent vocabulary is translated in general. It should be borne in mind that the transfer of equivalent terms does not allow an approximate translation, since the state of "proximity" itself contradicts the accurate transmission of information [7, p. 245-246].

Material of research. To analyze the features of the translation of medical terminology, one of the types of medical text was chosen - instructions for the use of medicines. Two instructions for the use of such drugs as Nurofen 200 mg Coated Tablets (in English) and Nurofen (in Russian) were used as a source of research material. For the presented analysis, we took the current versions of the instructions texts (last update in 2017). During the analysis of translation transformations in the English and Russian versions of the instructions for the use of the drug Nurofen, 136 language pairs of terminological units were identified. The results of the study. Each language pair from the terminological units selected by the continuous sampling method was analyzed in terms of the following criteria: 1) the structural type of the English and Russian term in a pair; 2) the origin of the English term (the original or borrowed term (depending on the source language)); 3) the used translation technique for transmission in PL.

When determining the structural organization of medical terms for instructions on the use of drugs, the taxonomy proposed by S. V. Shvetsova was chosen as a classification model [9, p. 15]. According to this classification, all terminological units are divided into the following groups:

- a) simple terms, which are understood as one-word terms, the foundations of which coincide with the root,
- b) complex terms, which are one-word terms, the basics of which contain several root morphemes,
- c) terminological combinations, i.e. terms formed by combining two or more terminological components. In accordance with the morphemic structure of the word, another type of terms stands out - abbreviations [4, p. 158].

The increase in the number of Russian translational terminological combinations is explained by the fact that Russian medical terms have a more complex structure than English, which, in turn, tend to save language costs [2, p. 911]. In addition, the data obtained during the analysis of medical terminology in the instructions for use in English and Russian show that the special medical vocabulary is mainly represented by terminological combinations both in English (78 units out of 136) and in Russian (89 units out of 136), which in turn confirms the point of view of modern scientists that the majority of the lexical fund in all terminological systems of medicine is composed of multicomponent terminological combinations [8, p. 20]. In the selected simple terminological units (30 terms in total), 77%, or 23 units, retained the structural type of the simple term in Russian. In the form of

terminological combinations, 7 units (23%) were transmitted.

As for abbreviations, in English and Russian, the number of such usage is 5 units (in each of the languages). Compared to other structural types, abbreviations are not represented in large volumes. However, if we take into account the fact that the selection was carried out only from the texts of the instructions of one preparation, then we can draw a preliminary conclusion that abbreviations are a quite often used method of designating terminological units.

Studying the history of the formation of the language of medical science and the sources of terminological units made it possible to distribute all the selected English terms into the following groups [10; eleven]:

1. terms that are wholly or partially Greek or Latin origin: 76 terms (56%) (concomitant therapy; dyspnoea; haematoma; clinical particulars; list of excipient (s); gastric emptying; abdominal pain; acute renal failure);
2. primordial terms: 54 terms (39%) (head colds; skin rashes; corticosteroids; marketing authorization holder; shelf life; blister tray; low dose; Stevens-Johnson syndrome);
3. terms having a full or partial French origin: 5 terms (4%) (diuretics; sucrose; deterioration; vomiting; acetylsalicylic acid);
4. term of Italian origin: 1 term (1%) (influenza).

The following regularity in the use of borrowings was noted: terms of Greek, Latin or French origin for the most part comprise a terminological subgroup of names of diseases and symptoms, which in most cases are translated using methods of

transcription or transliteration (partial or complete), for example, abdominal pain - abdominal pain (partial transliteration and tracing); epidermal necrolysis - epidermal necrolysis (partial transliteration); acute renal failure - acute renal failure (tracing); aseptic meningitis - aseptic meningitis (partial transliteration); bronchial asthma - bronchial asthma (complete and partial transcription); diarrhea - diarrhea (partial transliteration)).

In addition, the terms of the category of pharmacological names include the vocabulary of the field of chemistry, and most of the names of the field of chemistry have a similar form in different languages due to their common Latin or Greek origin, therefore, the translation of such units is carried out mainly through transliteration or transcription. In turn, primordial terms to a fairly equal extent represent the terms of all categories, with the exception of the category of names of diseases, where terminological units are more often represented by primordial terms, compared with the terms of other subgroups. For example, backache, Crohn's Disease, drowsiness, head colds, headache, heart failure, period pain, skin rashes, Stevens-Johnson syndrome. Terms of French and Italian origin are mostly translated by transcribing and transliterating (partial or full) or selecting a stable lexical unit: diuretics - diuretics (partial transliteration); sucrose - sucrose (selection of a stable lexical unit); deterioration - deterioration (selection of a stable lexical unit); vomiting - vomiting (selection of a stable lexical unit); acetylsalicylic acid - acetylsalicylic acid (tracing and partial transliteration); influenza - influenza (selection of a stable lexical unit).

A general study of the used translation techniques of medical terms in the text of the instructions revealed the following patterns:

A) in most cases, the translation of terminological units in the texts of the instructions is based on the selection in the PL of existing established lexical correspondences. In the material studied, 50 medical terms (37%) were transmitted in Usbek in the form of lexical units traditionally used in the corresponding meaning, for example, nature and contents of container - release form; coadministration - concurrent administration; bronchospasm in response to aspirin - "aspirin" bronchial asthma; clinical particulars - pharmacological action; interaction with other medicinal products - drug interaction, etc.;

B) another common way of transferring to YP is tracing technique, with the help of which 27 terminological units were transmitted in Russian, which amounted to 20% of the total number of terms in the instructions, for example, Crohn's Disease - Crohn's disease; skin rashes - skin rash; contraindications - contraindications; dental pain - toothache;

C) for 8% of the terms, or 11 units, the method of transmission to PL was the method of explication, for example, a coated tablet — coated tablets; erythema multiforme - erythema multiforme exudative; name of the medicinal product - international nonproprietary name; fever - fever;

D) the transfer of 8 units (6%) in Russian was carried out using full or partial transliteration, for example, thrombocytopenia - thrombocytopenia; anti-coagulants - anticoagulants; diuretics -

diuretics; talc - talc; Macrogol 6000 - Macrogol 6000;

The terms of the section for the names of diseases and symptoms are translated mainly by transcription, transliteration and tracing, for example, abdominal pain - abdominal pain; cardiac glycosides - cardiac glycosides; bronchial asthma - bronchial asthma; thrombocytopenia - thrombocytopenia; skin rashes - skin rash; muscular strain - muscle pains. In addition, the presence of a large number (33 units - 24%) of commonly used terms, which more often refer to the group of terms for the names of diseases and symptoms, was noted in the composition of the selected terminological material.

Conclusions. An analysis of two instructions for the use of medicines Nurofen 200 mg Coated Tablets (in English) and Nurofen (in Russian), revealed the most common translation

techniques for the transfer of medical terms in YP, which include the selection of an established lexical correspondence, a combination of several techniques, tracing and explication. It is important to note that when translating medical terminology, general lexical and grammatical transformations are used that are used in texts of any genre. A large percentage of terms translated using the selection of a stable lexical unit, as well as explication, indicates that medical terminology in Russian has its own established linguistic tradition, while methods of tracing, transliteration and transcription draw attention to the fact that medical terminology in general has an international character, shows a tendency to maintain lexical unity due to the desire to copy special vocabulary from one language to another.

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